

EFFECT OF SURFACE TREATMENTS ON THERMAL STABILITY OF CURAUA FIBERS

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ABSTRACT

Natural fibers as reinforcement in polymer composites requires investigation to better understand their behaviour and which treatments are more efficient to improve the interaction between fibers and polymer matrices, since, the quality of the surface treatment could improve the mechanical properties. The primary objective of this work is to evaluate the effect of alkali and silane treatments on the chemical, thermal and morphological properties of curaua fibers (*Ananas erectifolius*), a plant derived from Amazon region. The curaua fibers were treated by solutions of Ba(OH)₂ 10% (w/v), Ca(OH)₂ 14% (w/v), NaOH 5% (w/v), KOH 10% (w/v) or silane 5% (w/v). We used thermogravimetry and its derivative curves (TG-DTG), Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), X-ray diffraction and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) to evaluate the treated fibers. TG-DTG analysis was used to determine fibers thermal behaviour. This analysis revealed that the curaua treated with Ca(OH)₂ 14% (w/v) and silane 5% (w/v) presented the highest thermal stability compared to the untreated curaua fibers. The FTIR results showed a reduction of the peak of the band present in the infrared region between 1430-1448 cm⁻¹, as a consequence of the chemical treatments, partially removing the hemicellulose and lignin portions. SEM analysis revealed fibers defibrillation for fibers chemically treated. Finally, the fibers treated by the different chemical reagents increased the index of crystallinity, evidencing the partial removal of lignin and hemicellulose from the fibers, as well as increasing the contact surface of the fibers, thus, the treatments are efficient in increasing the crystallinity of the curaua fibers and removal of amorphous constituents.

1 INTRODUCTION

Lignocellulosic fibers instead synthetic fibers could promote advantages for materials industry because of their low cost, low density and biodegradability. Due to chemical structure based on hydroxyls groups, the surface treatments are easy and can improve the interaction between hydrophilic and hydrophobic materials, as polymers [1]. Natural fibers are composed basically by cellulose, lignin, hemicellulose and other components with low molecular weight, as wax and inorganic substances. Besides the surface treatment, the lignin, hemicellulose and impurities removal can facilitate the adhesion between fibers and polymer matrices [2].

Then, the surface treatments are capable to remove amorphous components from the fibers and adding functional groups that can allow better bonding with polymer [2]. For fibers treatment, various chemical reagents can be applied to remove the chemical components, as lignin and hemicellulose, or modify the chemical structure of cellulose [2-5]. In previous work in the literature, the alkaline treatments can remove amorphous components and surface impurities from untreated fibers, increasing the surface roughness and the cellulose content [2-4]. Other authors proved the chemical modification with silane agent decreases the hydrophilicity in the fibers increasing compatibility with polymers [2-5].

In this context, a lignocellulosic fiber or natural fiber that has been attracting industry attention is curaua (*Ananas erectifolius*) fiber. The plant is native from Amazon region and it is usually applied to manufacture of ropes and hammock [3]. The main attention for curaua fiber is due to its composition

with high cellulose content (65%), 15% hemicellulose and 7.3% lignin [5]. The lignin content in the fiber is lower than in other types of lignocellulosic fibers, such as jute, sugarcane bagasse and coconut. Due to its high cellulose content, curaua fiber has a high degree of crystallinity (67-75%) and higher values of tensile strength and elasticity modulus than other natural fibers, which can be applied as a potential composite reinforcement [5].

Then, the objective of this work is evaluating the effect of different surface treatments on the chemical, thermal stability and morphology properties of curaua fiber, seeking for the potential application in composites.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

Curaua fibers (average length of 80 cm) were kindly supplied by CEAPAC from Santarém - Brazil. Before the treatments, curaua fibers were cut to a 5-6 cm length.

2.2 Fibers chemical modification

Five different treatments were performed for curaua fibers: 1) Ba(OH)₂ 10% (w/v) – solution mixture at ratio of 10: 1 (solution: fiber) for 48 h at room temperature ($\approx 25^\circ\text{C}$); 2) Ca(OH)₂ 14% (w/v) - at ratio of 10: 1 (solution: fiber) at 70°C for 4 h under manual stirring; 3) NaOH 5% (w/v) - the fibers were mercerized at ratio of 10: 1 (solution: fiber) at 70°C for 2 h under manual stirring; 4) KOH 10% (w/v) - the fibers were soaked at distilled water in a ratio of 10: 1 (water/ fiber) for 1 h at room temperature and then filtered. Then, the fibers were immersed in KOH and mechanically stirred at 50 rpm and orbital agitation of 150 rpm simultaneously for 3h at room temperature; and 5) trimethoxy(propyl) silane 5% (w/v) - Firstly, the fibers were mercerized in a NaOH solution 5% (w/v) at ratio of 10: 1 (solution: fiber) at 45°C for 6 h under manual stirring. Finally, the fibers were mercerized in a silane methanol solution 5% (w/v) at pH 4 controlled by glacial acetic acid addition. The fibers were immersed in a silane solution for 4 h at room temperature. In all treatments the fibers were washed with distilled water until neutral pH and dried at room temperature for 120 h.

2.3 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

Before observation, the surface of the curaua fibers was coated with gold. Then, the surface morphology of the curaua were investigated by SEM (Jeol JSM-7001F) operated with 15 kV and emission current of 81 μA .

2.4 Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)

FTIR spectra of the curaua fibers were obtained by using Fourier transform infrared spectrometer (NICOLET IS10 da Thermo Scientific) with diffuse reflectance accessory (DRIFT). Each spectrum was recorded in the range of $400\text{--}4000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} and 128 scans.

2.5 X-ray diffraction (XRD)

XRD analyses of untreated and treated curaua fibers were performed by RIGAKI (ULTIMAV) X-Ray diffractometer using CuK α radiation and operating at reflection mode with an incident angle of 1.54 Å. The diffraction intensities of the curaua fibers were recorded between 5° and 50° (2θ) at $3^\circ/\text{min}$. The crystallinity indexes were calculated by following Segal empirical method, as showed in Eq.1 [6]:

$$\% X_c = \frac{(I_{002} - I_{am})}{I_{002}} \times 100 \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

Where I_{002} ($2\theta = 22.5^\circ$) and I_{am} ($2\theta = 18^\circ$) are the maximum intensity of the crystalline peak and the amorphous halo, respectively.

2.6 Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA)

The samples were analysed under a heating rate of 5 °C/ min from 25 to 600 °C in a simultaneous (TGA-DSC) thermal analyser Q600 SDT equipment (TA Instruments, USA) and nitrogen atmosphere at rate flow of 50 mL/min. Samples with 10 ± 0.5 mg were deposited in an alumina pan.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Scanning electron microscopy analysis

After the treatments, SEM analysis (Fig. 1) revealed different levels of defibrillation depending on the treatment. The Fig. 1A shows a cohesive structure between cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin [7]. Although the fibrillar structure, the untreated fibers do not show defibrillation. In addition, it can be seen after the mercerization process (Fig. 1B, 1C, 1D, 1E and 1F), the surface of the fibers had become rougher and reduced in diameter due to the removal of the amorphous components [8]. The chemical process involved in the removal of these constituents occurs through the action of the reagents on the rupture of the hydrogen bonds, which in contact with the hydroxyl group (-OH) of hemicellulose and lignin, cause defibrillation [9].

Figure 1: SEM images (500X magnification) for untreated curaua fiber (A) and treated with $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ (B), $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ (C), KOH (D), NaOH (E) and silane (F).

Micrographs of $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ and $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ treated fibers (Fig. 1B and 1C, respectively) show the treatment was able to remove constituents from the surface of the fibers, causing defibrillation. It was also found that in Fig. 1D and 1E, for fibers treated with KOH and NaOH solution, exhibited a more pronounced exposure of the fibrils, which promoted an efficient components removal, increasing surface roughness of the exposed fibrils. The increased roughness is a consequence of the removal of hemicellulose, lignin and waxy coatings [10]. A more rugged surface is beneficial for a subsequent adhesion between the fiber and a polymer matrix [7-10].

A surface with high fibrils portion can be observed in the micrograph of the silane-treated fiber (Fig. 1E), due to the breakage of the hydrogen bonds, a smooth and free surface can be observed. This smoothness feature is attributed to deposited polysiloxane surface layer on fiber, this layer can be responsible for the compatibility between fiber and matrix, decreasing the polarity of the fiber and improving fiber adhesion to polymeric materials [8-11].

3.2 Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy analysis

Fig. 2 shows the FTIR spectra for the untreated and treated curaua fibers. The bands for all fibers

present typical peaks for main lignocellulosic components according to the literature [11-12-13]. It is also observed that after the chemical modification process there was an increase in the peak intensity around 893 cm^{-1} in all spectra from treated curaua fibers, due to the removal of amorphous constituents, keeping the presence of cellulose, which its band corresponds to the stretching of the C-H glycosidic linkages. In a similar study, conducted by Vishnu [14] where banana fiber was treated with different reagents, the same pattern of peak intensity was observed after the treatments applied.

It has been shown that the peaks at $1520\text{-}1690\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for the untreated fibers are typical peaks for plant fibers presenting a lignin structure in this region. This band is attributed to the stretching of the C=O and C=C bonds conjugated with lignin aromatic rings [13]. It is observed that after the alkaline treatments, a reduction of the peaks in this region occurred, confirming lignocellulosic components removal by alkaline solution [12]. The same happened with the fibers treated with silane that presented spectrum similar to those treated with alkali. However, according to Mahesha [15], which reported similar behaviour for the *grewia serrulata* fibers treated with a concentration of silane 1% (w/v), the bands of this region are associated with the stretching of Si-O-Si [15].

Figure 2: FTIR spectra for curaua fibers.

The spectra for $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$, $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ and silane treated fibers in the present band between $1700\text{-}1734\text{ cm}^{-1}$ showed similar band patterns with a reduction of the peak in respect to untreated fiber spectrum. Spectra for fibers treated with KOH and NaOH showed that hemicellulose was almost completely removed, evidenced by the disappearing of carbonyl group stretching C=O bonds [16].

The peaks around 2922 cm^{-1} are attributed to the stretching of cellulose and hemicellulose of the functional group C-H. It was observed these peaks had reduced intensity in the fibers treated with alkaline solution, resulting in cellulose and hemicellulose removal [14]. In addition, it was shown that the spectrum of the silane treated fiber increased the intensity of this peak, indicating that the silane was more selective in the removal of hemicellulose, giving a greater exposure to the cellulose present in the fiber [17-18]. It is pertinent to mention that the long peak around 3400 cm^{-1} is a result of the vibration of the O-H stretch commonly present in cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin structures [19].

3.3 X-ray diffraction analysis

The crystallinity index represents the amount of cellulose present in the plant fibers. This component gives the lignocellulosic fibers rigidity and flexibility due to their structure, which has a large number of strong molecular bonds in the regions [20]. Fig. 3 shows the X-ray diffraction pattern obtained for

analyzed samples.

Figure 3: XRD spectra for untreated and treated curaua fibers.

According to Fig. 3 it is possible to observe the XRD spectrum for the curaua samples treated and not chemically treated. Note that all the analyzed fiber samples presented similar diffraction behavior, with three main reflection peaks, varying only their intensities. The first peak observed at $2\Theta = 16^\circ$ is attributed to the crystallographic plane (0 0 -1), the second peak $2\Theta = 22.5^\circ$ corresponds to the crystallographic plane (0 0 2) and the third peak $2\Theta = 34.5^\circ$ is associated with the crystallographic plane (0 40), all peaks characteristic of cellulose I [21]. As previously mentioned, there was a change in the peaks intensity for the analyzed fibers, which shows that depending on the treatment applied, there is a crystallinity increases, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: crystallinity index for untreated and treated curaua fibers.

Samples	%Xc
Untreated fibers	55.96
Ba(OH) ₂	62.34
Ca(OH) ₂	59.77
KOH	67.29
NaOH	62.18
Silane	64.47

According to the values described in Table 1, it is observed that the crystallinity index of the curaua fibers treated with alkali and silane are higher than the untreated fibers. The higher crystallinity index for the treated curaua fibers in respect to the untreated fibers suggested the chemical process was able to cause amorphous portions removal. Therefore, based on the XRD analysis, it is assumed that the modification of the curaua fiber using alkaline solution and silane solution were able to make a reorganization of the structural characteristics, besides increasing the crystalline behavior of the curaua fiber. Erdoğan et al. [2] in a chemical modification study of jute fiber treated with NaOH 5% (w/v) solution and silane 5% (w/v) solution, presented the same pattern of increase in crystallinity index.

3.4 Thermogravimetric Analysis

In Fig. 4, the TG and DTG curves for the curaua samples are shown. The presence of three characteristic thermal events for untreated fibers can be observed in the DTG curves. The first event, which occurred at a temperature lower than 100 °C, which is related to moisture loss [22]. The second event is attributed to degradation of lignin and hemicellulose, which degraded at range around 200-300 °C. Lignin pyrolysis is a slow and almost constant process that starts at lower temperatures by

approximately 140 °C varying up to 600 °C. This stage of degradation gives to lignin a high thermal stability due to its complex network structure of reticulated aromatic molecules that are difficult to decompose [23-24]. The hemicellulose pyrolysis in a range that varies between 220-300 °C [25]. The third thermal event in the range of 330-400 °C corresponds to cellulose degradation, cellulose pyrolysis has a higher peak than other peaks. This peak intensity means that cellulose degrades faster and its unbranched crystalline structure [24-26].

Figure 4: Thermal stability for untreated and treated curaua fibers.

Also, according to Fig. 4, the disappearance of the peak corresponding to the degradation of the amorphous components for the treated curaua on the surface is remarkable, with the same pattern of removal from the organic constituents studied by XRD, FTIR and MEV characterization.

Table 2: Thermal properties of the untreated and treated curaua fibers.

Samples	Thermal stability (°C)	T _{peak} (°C)	T _{onset} (°C)	T _{peak} (C°)	Residue at 600 °C
Untreated Fibers	312.43	273.09	317.29	344.25	13.17
Ba(OH) ₂	252.38	-	309.75	343.95	17.88
Ca(OH) ₂	314.88	-	318.92	340.74	15.71
KOH	267.17	-	303.79	339.21	19.12
NaOH	273.27	-	303.64	340.06	17.96
Silane	317.38	-	321.05	341.88	14.59

Table 2 shows the data related to the thermal behavior of the curaua fibers. According to the data obtained the thermal stability varied between 252.38 and 317.38 °C, however, it is noticed that the fibers treated with Ba(OH)₂, KOH, NaOH had a lower stability than the untreated fibers. This means that there was actually lignin removal from the treated fibers, as this component pyrolysis at higher temperatures, so with the removal of this constituent the treated fibers start to degrade earlier [25]. Moreover, it is observed that the thermal behavior of Ca(OH)₂ treated fibers is slightly more thermally stable compared to untreated fibers, suggesting that this treatment was more effective in the removal of lignin. The silane-treated fibers also showed superior thermal stability to untreated fibers, this is attributed to the difficult

decomposition of the polysiloxane (Si-O-Si) bonds that bind to the OH group of the fibers, forming a rigid layer on the material [27-28]. According to Eng [29], this same behavior was observed in their study, where after the treatment with silane agent, the thermal stability of oil palm mesocarp fibers was superior to that untreated fiber.

9 CONCLUSIONS

As evidenced by XRD and FTIR, all treatments were able to remove part of the lignin and hemicellulose. The removal of amorphous components increased the crystallinity index, causing marginal changes in thermal stability, except for Ca(OH)₂ and silane treatments, which suggests that the lignin removal was more effective in these treatments. Overall, the thermal stability for the treated fibers was significantly lower due to the treatments applied, as they were able to partially remove the lignin, which is more thermally constituent stable *in natural* fibers, this removal is also supported by SEM images. In addition, the crystallinity index of the fibers increased after the treatments improving the order of packing of the crystalline cellulose. Therefore, it was concluded that both the alkaline treatment and the silane treatment are effective for the curaua fiber, promoting removal of amorphous components, increasing the thermal stability of the treated fibers.

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